

were heated up to 50° on a water bath. The reagent solution was added dropwise with constant stirring. The complex thus formed was filtered, washed, dried and weighed as described earlier. The ions Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , PO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ do not interfere in the gravimetric estimation of Bi(III).

Composition of the Complex: From analytical data on carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents the bismuth complex has the composition corresponds to the $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ONS}_2)_3$ (found C, 25.72, H, 3.92 and N, 5.88 Calc. C, 25.89, N, 3.47 and N, 6.04 per cent.), where the ligand is presumably bidentate. The conductometric titrations also confirm this stoichiometry.

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Some Phenoxyacetyl Thiosemicarbazides, Substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, 1,2,4-Triazoles and Alkyl/Phenyl Carbamates of Substituted 1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-Thiones

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A large number of thiosemicarbazides have been reported to possess good antibacterial¹, antifungal^{2,3}, herbicidal⁴ and anticholinesterase⁵ activities. Substituted 1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles and 1, 2, 4-triazoles obtained from cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides with iodine and NaOH respectively are also known to possess similar biological activities⁶⁻¹⁰. Moreover, recently many carbamate derivatives have found world-wide application as potent insecticide^{11,12}. With this view in mind several thiosemicarbazides(I), oxadiazoles(II) and triazoles(III) carbamates(IV) have been synthesised in the laboratory to study their insecticidal and other biological properties.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Elemental

analysis (N) were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical value for all the compounds prepared.

Aryloxyacetyl hydrazines were prepared by the method of L. Conti^{1,3}.

Aryl isothiocyanates were prepared by the method of Dains^{1,4}.

1-Aryloxyacetyl-4-aryl-3-thiosemicarbazides(I)—A mixture of aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) and aryl isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on steam bath for 2-3 hr and the solid product separated was crystallised from ethanol. The relevant data are placed in Table 1.

2-Aryloxymethyl-5-arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazoles(II)—were prepared according to the method of Paul and Basu^{1,5}, from the appropriate thiosemicarbazide with iodine in potassium iodide solution in presence of NaOH, and the crude solid product finally obtained was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, the data are placed in Table 1.

3-Aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles(III)—The solution obtained by heating a mixture of compound (I, 0.01 mole) and NaOH (2N, 20 ml) under reflux for 1 hr was acidified with dilute HCl and filtered. The desired solid product after washing with water was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

3-Hydroxymethyl 5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones were synthesised according to the reported method^{1,6}.

Alkyl and aryl-[5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione-3-methyl]-carbamates(IV)—0.01 mole of 3-hydroxymethyl 5-(substituted phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione and 0.01 mole of phenyl/alkyl isocyanate were refluxed in dry benzene or dry dichloromethane-ether (50 : 50) with one drop of triethylamine for 6-10 hr. After distilling the solvent, solid residue obtained was crystallised from benzene. The compounds thus synthesised are recorded in Table 2.

Biological Activity: The compounds listed in Tables 1 and 2 were evaluated for their inhibitory effects against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus magaterium* by agar diffusion technique¹⁷. Compound Nos. 2,9,11, 12,14,16,22,27,28,31,34,36,40,41,43,44,47,49,50 and 51 inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, and Compound Nos. 2,3,5,7,9,11,13,14,16,18,20,27,30,31,32,36,38,40, 43,44,45 and 49 showed inhibition against *S. typhi*. Inhibition against *S. aureus* was observed in Compound Nos. 5,7,9,14,17,19,22,27,28,30,36,40,41,43,44 and 47. Compound Nos. 5,7,13,14,18,19,20,22,27,30, 34,36,40,43,44 and 47 showed inhibition against *B. magaterium*. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I. Lucknow were used.

NOTES

TABLE-1

I

II

III

Sl. N.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Sl. N.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Sl. N.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	2,4-Di-Cl	2-OCH ₃	177	78	13.*	2,4-Di-Cl	3-CH ₃	151-2	50	20.	2,4-Di-Cl	2-OCH ₃	178	75
2.	2,4-Di-Cl	4-OCH ₃	166	75	14.	2,4-Di-Cl	2-OCH ₃	147	54	21.	2,4-Di-Cl	4-OCH ₃	187	70
3.	2,4-Di-Cl	3-CH ₃	157-58	74	15.	4-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	145	50	22.	2,4-Di-Cl	3-CH ₃	189	70
4.	4-Cl	H	169-70	88	16.	4-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	118	54	23.*	4-Cl	H	212	78
5.*	4-Cl	3-CH ₃	161	65	17.	4-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	141	57	24.	4-Cl	3-CH ₃	208	70
6.	4-Cl	4-CH ₃	166	68	18.	4-Cl	H	140-1	64	25.	4-Cl	4-CH ₃	211-12	75
7.	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	163	68	19.	4-Cl	4-OCH ₃	169-70	58	26.	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	197	70
8.	4-Cl	4-OCH ₃	162-3	72						27.	4-Cl	4-OCH ₃	203-5	70
9.	4-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	161	72						28.	4-CH ₃	3-CH ₃	194	72
10.	4-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	153	75						29.	4-CH ₃	4-CH ₃	181	72
11.	4-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	150-151	70						30.	4-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	185-86	70
12.	4-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	148	70						31.	4-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	148-49	72

*i.r. absorption, CONHNH, 2900 and 3300 cm⁻¹
CO 1700 cm⁻¹
NHCS 1360 cm⁻¹

*i.r. absorption, NH, 3360 cm⁻¹
OCN 1640 cm⁻¹
NCN 1585 cm⁻¹

*i.r. absorption NH 3200 cm⁻¹
C=N 1600 cm⁻¹
C=S 1320 cm⁻¹

TABLE-2

IV

Sl. N.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Sl. N.	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %
32.	C ₆ H ₅	4-Cl	150	90	43.	n-C ₄ H ₉	2-OH ₃	92	56
33.	CH ₃	4-Cl	145	59	44.	C ₆ H ₅	2,4-Di-Cl	152	89
34.	n-C ₃ H ₇	4-Cl	101	57	45.	CH ₃	2,4-Di-Cl	96	58
35.	n-C ₃ H ₇	4-Cl	75	60	46.	n-C ₃ H ₇	2,4-Di-Cl	93	50
36.	C ₆ H ₅	4-CH ₃	152	86	47.	n-C ₄ H ₉	2,4-Di-Cl	90	57
37.	CH ₃	4-CH ₃	114	58	48.	C ₆ H ₅	3-CH ₃	109	90
38.	n-C ₃ H ₇	4-CH ₃	117	56	49.	CH ₃	3-CH ₃	103	59
39.	n-C ₄ H ₉	4-CH ₃	106	58	50.	n-C ₃ H ₇	3-CH ₃	100	60
40.	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH ₃	154	89	51.	n-C ₄ H ₉	3-CH ₃	93	55
41.	CH ₃	2-CH ₃	140	56					
42.	n-C ₃ H ₇	2-CH ₃	112	57					

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Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Breynia rhamnoids* Muell (Euphorbiaceae)

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BREYNIA rhamnoids Muell, commonly known as 'Surasaruni' grows throughout tropical India. Its different parts are indigenously used as local remedies for different diseases¹. The bark is astringent and its leaves are extensively used in the treatment of tonsils, uvula. No work seems to have been done on the leaves of this plant and hence a systematic study of this part was undertaken.

Dried and powdered leaves were thoroughly extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was taken in ether and separated into acidic and neutral fractions.

Neutral fraction :

This was chromatographed over deactivated alumina whereupon the following compounds were obtained :

n-Alkanes : Elution of the column with petroleum ether afforded a crystalline product m.p. 52-60°. GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of *n*-alkanes² (C₂₆-C₃₄); *n*-triacontane (51.8%), *n*-dotriacontane (21.1%), *n*-nonacosane (8.3%), *n*-octacosane (6.0%), *n*-hentriacontane (5.3%), *n*-tri-triacontane (3.6%), and the minor quantities of *n*-hexacosane, *n*-heptacosane and *n*-tetratriacontane.

Aliphatic Alcohol : Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1, v/v) furnished ceryl alcohol³, m.p. 75°. It was identified on the basis of I.R., m.m.p. and by preparing its acetate, m.p. 60-62°.

Triterpenes : Elution of the column with benzene yielded a crystalline solid m.p. 137-139°, which responds to positive Liebermann Burchard test for triterpenes, GC-MS showed it to be a mixture of eight triterpenes. One of them, lanosterol⁴, m.p. 139-140° was separated and identified by m.m.p. determination, Co-TLC and Co-IR with an authentic specimen. Others are under process.

Phytosterol : Elution with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1, v/v) gave a white crystalline solid, m.p. 122-128°. GC-MS analysis of the substance (as trimethyl silyl ether derivative) showed it to be a mixture⁵ of cholesterol (0.4%) (M⁺ 458), campesterol (1.07%) (M⁺ 472), stigmasterol (4.82%) (M⁺ 484), β -sitosterol (92.55%) (M⁺ 486) and an unidentified substance mixed with sitosterol (1.07%), the two ion peaks 343, 386 are different from the β -sitosterol.

Acidic fraction :

The acidic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with ether-petroleum ether (1 : 9, v/v) gave a product, m.p. 65-69°. Its methyl ester melted at 59-62° and GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of *n*-pentatriacontanoic (19.33%), *n*-triacontanoic (19.13%), *n*-tetracosanoic (17.23%), *n*-tricosanoic (15.75%), *n*-octacosanoic (3.24%), *n*-dotriacontanoic (3.21%), *n*-heptatriacontanoic (2.46%), *n*-hexacosanoic (2.00%), *n*-octatriacontanoic (1.80%) acids, along with the minor quantities of *n*-tetra-triacontanoic, *n*-cosanoic, *n*-pentacosanoic, *n*-heptacosanoic, *n*-hentriacontanoic, *n*-nonacosanoic, *n*-tri-triacontanoic and *n*-hexatriacontanoic acids.

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